

确定高新技术产品开发阶段的价格

DETERMINING THE PRICE OF INNOVATIVE HIGH-TECH PRODUCTS AT THE STAGE OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

Khrustalev Evgeniy Yurievich

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Chief Researcher

Larin Sergey Nikolaevich

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Leading research worker

Central Economics and Mathematics Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences

抽象的。文章展示了俄罗斯高科技综合体企业在国内经济现代化及其向创新发展转型中发挥的日益重要的作用。事实证明,需要开发新的、有效的组织和经济机制及工具,以实现适合现代条件的研发成果的商业化。提出通过确定科技产品开发阶段的价格来解决研发成本优化问题。

关键词: 企业、创新、高科技综合体、研发成果商业化。

Abstract. *The article shows the growing role of enterprises of the Russian high-tech complex in the modernization of the domestic economy and the implementation of its transition to innovative development. The need to develop new and effective organizational and economic mechanisms and tools for the commercialization of R&D results that are adequate to modern conditions is substantiated. A solution to the problem of optimizing R&D costs is proposed by determining the price of scientific and technical products at the stage of their development.*

Keywords: *enterprises, innovations, high-tech complex, commercialization of R&D results.*

Introduction

At the present stage of socio-economic development of the world community, the dominant paradigm has become the use of high technologies, new scientific knowledge, and the introduction of innovations as leading factors in ensuring effective economic growth and national competitiveness. Developed Western countries took the path of creating a “new economy” in the early 1990s of the last century. About 10 years later, they were joined by a number of newly industrialized (South Korea, Taiwan, China) and developing countries (India, South Africa). The fundamental difference between the “new economy” and the traditional one is that

intangible assets, such as theoretical knowledge, scientific and technical developments, and, above all, innovation, become the determining factors of production.

The new order of social and economic relations in the modern economy has the following characteristics:

1) dynamics, which are characterized by a rapid increase in the pace of change in markets (there is a constant emergence of new players, more advanced technologies, products, etc., which are actively displacing old ones;

2) innovation, new business approaches and management methods, new developments and flexibility become the most important attributes of a successful business;

3) there is a qualitative development of mass production, which merges with specialization for the needs of each individual consumer;

4) scientific achievements and developments become the engine of other industries;

5) the development of network cooperation sharply reduces the importance of the distance between economic agents from the standpoint of managing them, which ensures the growth of decentralization, which is so necessary for flexible and specialized business;

6) the effective use of information and communication technologies is becoming a vital necessity for the competitiveness of both individual enterprises and the country as a whole.

Innovation activity in the world's leading economies

The economic essence of innovation lies in obtaining the final result of innovation activity, embodied in the form of a new or improved product (service) sold on the market, as well as a new or improved technological process used in practical activities [1]. In accordance with international methodological recommendations and standards (Oslo Manual, 2005), four main types of innovations are widely used abroad in public life - product, process, marketing and organizational, which determine their economic essence [2].

As world experience shows, effective innovation is possible if at least the following conditions are present:

- state support at the stages of R&D, formation of intellectual property objects (IPO) and creation of prototypes;

- creation of appropriate conditions and developed infrastructure for the practical implementation of innovations at the stage of R&D implementation;

- expansion of sources of financing innovative activities by attracting private investors at the stage of commercialization of R&D results.

However, the interests of private investors and the state when carrying out innovative activities do not always coincide. In most cases, the main goals of private entrepreneurs are the industrial development of R&D results with the launch

of new or improved products (services) on the market and increasing the capitalization of innovative enterprises created by them for the implementation of specific innovative projects. After reaching the peak of capitalization, the private investor seeks to sell his stake in the innovative enterprise and refocus on the implementation of a new innovative project. The goals of the state when implementing innovative projects are the introduction of new products to the market and their subsequent production, which contributes to the transition of production to a qualitatively higher level and increasing the competitiveness of domestic products in the domestic and international markets.

The initiative for the initial development of innovative industries in Western countries came from national governments concerned about strengthening their own defense capabilities. However, in contrast to the command economic system, the market model and comparative openness in developed countries made it possible for new technologies to flow smoothly into the private sector, where their further development took place. And now, by the beginning of the 21st century, investments from private companies have outstripped and many times exceeded budget expenditures.

The United States maintains a leading position in many indicators of the development of science and innovation. In 2019, they reached their historical maximum of spending on science - 3% of GDP. One of the main factors driving the growth of federal R&D funding in recent years has been the competitive struggle to maintain superiority in science and technology on the world stage. From 2000 to 2019, global U.S. R&D spending more than tripled in current dollars, from \$677 billion to \$2.2 trillion. However, the US share in these expenses decreased to 27% in 2019, with China taking second position (22%), followed by Japan (7%), Germany (6%) and South Korea (4%) [3].

According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) for 2019, the United States remains the leader in terms of R&D funding (\$657 billion). According to the National Science Foundation for 2019, the structure of US R&D funding looks like this: out of a total investment of \$657 billion:

- \$463.7 billion (70.6%) came from business,
- \$138.9 billion (21.2%) - from federal laboratories,
- \$21.8 billion (3.3%) - from universities and colleges,
- \$26.7 billion (4.1%) - from other non-profit organizations,
- \$5 billion (0.8%) was sent by state and local governments [4].

China ranks second (\$526 billion). It is constantly strengthening its position and is ahead of the top six world leaders in spending on science, such as Japan, Germany, South Korea and France combined. The 10 largest states funding R&D accounted for \$1.863 trillion in 2019, which is about 84.7% of global spending on science. The 20 leading countries accounted for \$2.078 trillion, or 94.5% of the global total [5].

The characteristic trend of science expenditures in global R&D expenditures in the period from 2000 to 2019 is Among the top 10 countries, six countries saw their share decline (USA, Japan, Germany, France, UK, and Italy), but four countries saw their share of spending increase (China, South Korea, Russia, and Taiwan). This indicates a shift in the global concentration of R&D from the developed countries of the USA and Europe to the countries of East, Southeast, and South Asia [6].

China has the highest rate of growth in R&D spending among major economies in the world. Its position has significantly strengthened in international patent activity and in knowledge-intensive and high-tech production. From 2000 to 2019 China's share of global R&D increased from 4.9 to 22%, while the US share fell from 39.8 to 27%, and Japan's share fell from 14.6 to 7%. In 2019, China's R&D increased by 13%, the highest among major economies in the world. China's innovation intensity rate almost tripled between 2000 and 2019 [7].

In addition, in actively developing countries, the state continues to actively support scientific activities by providing innovative enterprises with tax preferences and subsidies, low loans, grants, as well as through administrative measures.

Features of innovation development in Russia

The transition to an innovative path of development of Russian society predetermines the need to take into account the advanced achievements of scientific and technological progress in combination with the peculiarities of the development of the domestic economy. The basis of this approach is a continuous and targeted process of searching, preparing and practical implementation of product, technological, process and other innovations (innovations) that make it possible to increase the efficiency of the functioning of social production and the service sector, as well as the degree of realization of the ever-increasing needs of society. In order for the Russian Federation to take a significant place as one of the global leaders, it is necessary to achieve comparability of the technological base of the Russian economy with the leading countries of the modern world. In turn, innovation activity is one of the main drivers of economic growth in the Russian Federation [8].

In the Russian Federation, the volume of costs for innovation activities for 2010-2021. increased by 5.9 times and reached 2379.71 billion rubles. At the same time, in 2015 compared to 2014, there was a decrease in the indicator under consideration by 8.3 billion rubles. This is due to the financial crisis in 2014-2015, during which there was a deterioration in the overall economic situation in the country due to the introduction of economic sanctions. The largest increase in the amount of costs for the development of innovative activities of organizations occurred in 2019 compared to 2018 - by 481.3 billion rubles. (see Fig. 1 [9]).

Figure 1. Dynamics of costs for innovation activities in the Russian Federation (2010-2021), billion rubles

Source: compiled by the authors based on Rosstat data [9].

The share of innovative production in most sectors of the economy is very small. Qualified scientific, engineering and technical personnel are not fully utilized. The production base of the domestic economy is dominated by technological equipment of outdated structures, and its renewal is proceeding at a very slow pace. The exception to this is the high-tech complex (HTC), as well as the information and communication technology (ICT) sector. It seems obvious that the success of modernization and the transition of the Russian economy to innovative development will largely depend on the effective functioning of the MTC and the ICT sector.

MTC plays an important role in the economy, as it contributes to the development of innovation, increasing productivity and competitiveness of the country. MTC enterprises are a key factor in the economic development of the country since their innovative activities contribute to productivity growth, increasing the competitiveness of products, creating new jobs, attracting additional funds and developing the export of high-tech products and services.

The main prerequisite for the innovative development of MTC enterprises should be the emergence of promising R&D results for commercialization, a significant increase in their quality, as well as the ability to compete in domestic and foreign markets. The process of commercialization of R&D results consists of introducing new or improved products (services) to the market using the rights to create them [1]. It is no secret that due to the imperfection of the system of intel-

lectual capital management and organizational and economic support for commercialization that has developed at domestic high-tech enterprises, many promising R&D projects are not brought to the stage of commercial implementation in both the domestic and foreign markets.

The way out of this situation is seen in the need to develop new and effective organizational and economic mechanisms and tools for the commercialization of R&D results that are adequate to modern conditions. To do this, it is necessary to solve many problems facing MTC enterprises. One of the most important among them is the problem of optimizing R&D costs. This problem determines the importance of the task of improving the methodology for calculating the costs of R&D or the price of scientific and technical products (STP) when concluding contracts for their creation.

Since STP is a specific type of product, it can be assumed that, provided that the list of tasks initially agreed upon in the terms of reference remains constant throughout the entire period of its creation, the price of STP will depend on the following factors:

- demand for scientific and technological progress (its value for potential consumers);
- level of coordination of work during the development of scientific and technical progress;
- degree of importance of the consumer (customer);
- expected level of inflation;
- the number of main tasks solved in the process of creating scientific and technical progress.

When determining the costs of R&D, it is also necessary to take into account the tendency for the technical means that are used in the development of scientific and technological progress to become more expensive over time.

To take into account the influence of the above factors when determining the costs of R&D and forming the price of scientific and technical progress, it is necessary to use the appropriate coefficients. Calculation of the expected costs of the STP customer should be made, from our point of view, according to the following formula:

$$C_{HTII}(t_h, t_{OK}) = C_{HTII}^I(t_p, t_h, t_{OK}, \bar{R}_H^C(t_h, t_{OK})) + \Delta C(t_h, t_{OK}, \bar{R}_H^C(t_h, t_{OK}), \bar{R}_H^\Phi(t_h, t_{OK})) \quad (1)$$

where: t_h - planned date for the start of work on the creation of STP;

t_{OK} - planned date for the start of work on the creation of STP;

t_p - calculated point in time;

$C_{HTII}^I(t_p, t_h, t_{OK}, \bar{R}_H^C(t_h, t_{OK}))$ - planned (preliminary) price of scientific and technological progress (in prices of the estimated time t_p), created by the contractor in the period (t_h, t_{OK}) , with the inflation index agreed between the customer and the contractor for this period at the level $\bar{R}_H^C(t_h, t_{OK})$;

$\bar{R}_H^C(t_H, t_{OK})$ - the weighted average inflation index for the period (t_H, t_{OK}) agreed between the customer and the contractor, which corresponds to the preliminary price of scientific and technical progress;

$\bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK})$ - actual value of the weighted average inflation index during the period (t_H, t_{OK}) .

$\bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK}) = 1$, if $t_H = t_{OK}$ or during the period (t_H, t_{OK}) prices do not change, or inflationary and deflationary processes balance each other at this time.

$\bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK}) > 1$ if during the period (t_H, t_{OK}) there is an increase in the inflation index (the result of inflationary processes in the economy).

$\bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK}) < 1$ if during the period (t_H, t_{OK}) there is a fall in the inflation index (the result of deflationary processes in the economy);

$\Delta C(t_H, t_{OK}, \bar{R}_H^C(t_H, t_{OK}), \bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK}))$ - the amount of adjustment of the planned (preliminary) price based on the results of the inflation index actually prevailing in the country during the period (t_H, t_{OK}) .

Wherein:

$$\Delta C(t_H, t_{OK}, \bar{R}_H^C(t_H, t_{OK}), \bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK})) = 0, \text{ если } \bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK}) = \bar{R}_H^C(t_H, t_{OK}) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta C(t_H, t_{OK}, \bar{R}_H^C(t_H, t_{OK}), \bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK})) \neq 0 \text{ при } \bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK}) \neq \bar{R}_H^C(t_H, t_{OK}) \quad (3)$$

In this case, the value of the adjustment amount to the planned price is determined by the formula:

$$\Delta C(t_H, t_{OK}, \bar{R}_H^C(t_H, t_{OK}), \bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK})) = C_{HHP}^H(t_p, t_H, t_{OK}, R_H^C(t_H, t_{OK})) \left(\frac{\bar{R}_H^\phi(t_H, t_{OK})}{\bar{R}_H^C(t_H, t_{OK})} \right) \quad (4)$$

To obtain the value of the planned (preliminary) price of scientific and technological progress, it is advisable to use the concept of standard R&D - work on similar topics, for the implementation of which competitions were held in ministries and agencies of the Russian Federation. In this case, the data available in the catalog of R&D cost indicators can be used. The minimum price of R&D included in the same subclass with the planned R&D is taken as the base price.

The planned (preliminary) price of R&D should be determined by the formula:

$$C_{HHP}^H(t_p, t_H, t_{OK}, R_H^C(t_H, t_{OK})) = C_{HHP}^T(t_0) (\rho_{mc}^T R_{mc}^C(t_0, t_p) + R_H(t_0, t_p) (1 - \rho_{mc}^m)) \times \frac{R_H}{R_H^m} \times \frac{R_\alpha}{R_\alpha^m} \times \frac{R_O}{R_O^m} \times \frac{R_z}{R_z^m} \quad (5)$$

where: $C_{HHP}^T(t_0)$ - base price of typical R&D, calculated in point-in-time prices t_0 ;

$R_{mc}^C(t_0, t_p)$ - coefficient characterizing the degree of increase in the cost of technical equipment during the period (t_H, t_{OK}) acquired to carry out the planned R&D, compared with the cost of those funds that were purchased to carry out standard R&D;

ρ_{mc}^m - share of costs for the purchase of technical equipment in the price of standard R&D;

t_0 - the point in time in whose prices the price of standard R&D is calculated;

R_H - coefficient characterizing the value of scientific and technological progress;

R_u^m - coefficient characterizing the value of scientific and technological progress obtained during standard R&D;

R_α - coefficient characterizing the degree of importance of the customer for the planned R&D;

R_α^m - coefficient characterizing the degree of importance of the customer for typical R&D;

R_o - coefficient characterizing the role of the performer in organizing (coordinating) research and carrying out planned R&D;

R_o^m - coefficient characterizing the role of the performer in organizing (coordinating) research and performing standard R&D;

R_3 - coefficient characterizing the number of main tasks that require solutions in the process of performing planned R&D;

R_3^m - coefficient characterizing the number of main tasks that were solved in the process of performing standard R&D.

In the case when the necessary initial data are not available to estimate the value of the coefficient $R_{mc}^C(t_\sigma, t_p)$ the inflation index is used.

As initial information for determining values $\bar{R}_u^C(t_\sigma, t_p)$, $\bar{R}_p^\phi(t_u, t_{ok})$

$R_{mc}^C(t_\sigma, t_p)$, $R_u(t_\sigma, t_p)$ It is advisable to use data published by the State Statistics Committee of Russia, as well as planned indicators of price changes adopted by the Government of the Russian Federation.

When only the annual inflation index is known, and the periods of creation of scientific and technological progress cover only part of the i -th year, then to estimate the inflation index it is necessary to use the formula:

$$R(t_j, t_{j+1}) = R_i^{12 \frac{m_i}{12}} \quad (6)$$

where: m_i - the number of months in the i -th year that belong to the period (t_u, t_{ok}) ;

R_i - annual inflation index in the i -th year.

If the period (t_j, t_{j+1}) covers several years, then the inflation index should be determined by the formula:

$$R(t_j, t_{j+1}) = \prod_i R_i^{12 \frac{m_i}{12}} \quad (7)$$

The value of scientific and technological progress is determined by the level of novelty of the research that needs to be carried out to solve all the tasks set in the terms of reference and the level of quality of the results obtained. Therefore, the coefficient of value of scientific and technical progress is determined by the formula:

$$R_u = R_u^n \times R_u^{K^p} \times R_u^{K^{HMP}} \quad (8)$$

where: R_u^n - coefficient reflecting the level of novelty of scientific and technical progress;

$R_u^{K^p}$ - coefficient reflecting the predicted level of quality of the results expected to be obtained during the development of scientific and technical progress;

R_{ij}^{KHIP} - coefficient reflecting the a posteriori level of quality of results, determined based on the results of the planned R&D.

The values of the coefficient reflecting the level of novelty of scientific and technical progress vary from 1 (the work is aimed at clarifying individual results of a previously completed study) to 10 (the work is new, aimed at solving a newly emerging interdepartmental problem, developing the basic principles of theory and methodology).

The predicted level of research quality depends on the qualifications of R&D performers. An objective assessment of the qualifications of performers is whether they have academic degrees and academic titles. It is advisable to use these data as the basis for estimating the value of this coefficient based on the predicted quality of research results. The value of the coefficient, reflecting the a priori level of quality of the results, varies from 1 - work performed without the participation of candidates and doctors of science to 8 - work performed with the participation of doctors of science, professors (more than 10% of the number of performers). The value of the coefficient reflecting the a posteriori level of quality of the results is taken equal to one at the price negotiation stage. If any violations are detected on the part of the R&D contractor related to deviations from the tactical and technical specifications, the customer has the right to assign a value less than one to the coefficient reflecting the a posteriori level of quality of the results.

The values of the coefficient characterizing the role of the contractor in organizing (coordinating) research and performing planned R&D varies from 1 to 1.75, depending on the number of co-executors and their tasks.

Conclusion

As a result of the research, the following conclusions were formulated.

1. The active socio-economic growth of many countries is directly related to the development of science, education, development and implementation of innovative technologies and products that help meet consumer demand.

2. A characteristic trend in recent years has been a shift in the global concentration of R&D from the developed countries of the USA and Europe to the countries of East, Southeast and South Asia (China, South Korea, Taiwan), as well as to Russia.

3. In Russia for the period 2010-2021. There was also an increase in costs for innovation activities. MTC enterprises play an important role in the development of the Russian economy. They contribute significantly to the development of innovation, productivity and competitiveness. MTC enterprises are a key factor in economic development because their innovative activities ensure productivity growth, increase the competitiveness of products, create new jobs, attract additional funds and develop the export of high-tech products and services.

4. The model proposed by the authors formed the basis for the methodology for calculating the costs of R&D, the price of innovative high-tech products at the stage of their development, as well as determining the planned level of profitability of production for MTC enterprises. The application of this methodology contributed to increasing the efficiency of these enterprises. In addition, the proposed model was used in the development of methodological foundations for assessing the competitiveness of scientific and technological progress.

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